

Damage Quantification in Multi-directional Laminates using Thermoelastic Stress Analysis

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CERTIFICATION
FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE
TESTING PYRAMID

PRESENTATION OUTLINE

Project inspiration

Scientific background of TSA

Principles behind the damage parametrisation

Damage in multidirectional laminates

Conclusions of the research and future work

PROJECT AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

PREVIOUS WORK

Ruiz-Iglesias R., Ólafsson G., Thomsen OT., Dulieu-Barton JM.

Identification of Subsurface Damage in Multidirectional Composite Laminates Using Full-Field Imaging.

SEM 2022: Thermomechanics & Infrared Imaging, Inverse Problem Methodologies and Mechanics of Additive & Advanced Manufactured Materials, Volume 6. 2022. pp. 39–42. Available at: DOI:10.1007/978-3-031-17475-9_6

CFRP IM7/8552 $[90,0]_{3S}$ & $[0,90]_{3S}$

Analysis of the subsurface $\Delta T/T_0$ of CFRP $[0,90]_{3S}$ using the DIC surface ply model

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AIM & OBJECTIVES

Novel full-field damage parametrization methodology using TSA

- Exploit the non-adiabatic thermoelastic response to detect surface and subsurface damage in laminated composites.
- Damage quantification using TSA of CFRP $[0,90]_{3s}$, $[90,0]_{3s}$, $[0,45,-45,0,0,0]_s$ and $[0,0,0,45,-45,0]_s$ configurations.
- Compare TSA damage quantification with the stiffness degradation at different damage levels (obtained with DIC).
- **Work In Progress:** Applying all the knowledge to quantify damage in real structures (e.g C-Spar)

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Stress variation ($\Delta\sigma$) is required to obtain the thermoelastic response of a material:

T_0 ~ Mean temperature
 ρ ~ Density
 C_p ~ Specific heat capacity
 α_1 and α_2 ~ Thermal expansion coefficients in 1,2
 $\Delta\sigma_1$ and $\Delta\sigma_2$ ~ Stress variation in 1,2
 $[Q]_{1,2}$ ~ Stiffness matrix
 $[T]$ ~ Transformation matrix
 $[\Delta\varepsilon_{xy}]$ ~ Strain variation in x,y

$$\Delta T = \frac{-T_0}{\rho C_p} (\alpha_1 \Delta\sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta\sigma_2) = \frac{-T_0}{\rho C_p} \left([\alpha]_{1,2}^T [Q]_{1,2} [T] [\Delta\varepsilon]_{xy} \right)$$

Simplified for orthotropic composite lamina (as $\alpha_6 = 0$)

We are looking for HEAT TRANSFER to obtain SUBSURFACE INFO!

1,2: Ply coordinate system

x,y: Laminate coordinate system

Ply 1	→	ΔT (θ , Material properties, thickness...)
Ply 2	→	ΔT (θ , Material properties, thickness...)
Ply 3	→	ΔT (θ , Material properties, thickness...)
Ply n	→	ΔT (...)
Ply n+1	→	ΔT (...)

Midplane

Cross-section of multi-directional symmetric laminate

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Thermoelastic Stress Analysis on...

GFRP RP-528: Adiabatic for all the layups (Not subsurface contribution) [1]

CFRP IM7/8552 → HEAT TRANSFER OCCURING AT LOWER FREQUENCIES [1,2]

Subsurface Features (e.g. Damage)

Frequency Range

Example

[1] Jiménez-Fortunato I., Bull DJ., Thomsen OT., Dulieu-Barton JM. On the source of the thermoelastic response from orthotropic fibre reinforced composite laminates. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. Elsevier Ltd; 1 October 2021; 149(106515): 1–15.

[2] Ruiz-Iglesias R., Ólafsson G., Thomsen OT., Dulieu-Barton JM. Identification of Subsurface Damage in Multidirectional Composite Laminates Using Full-Field Imaging. *SEM 2022: Thermomechanics & Infrared Imaging, Inverse Problem Methodologies and Mechanics of Additive & Advanced Manufactured Materials*, Volume 6. 2022. pp. 39–42. Available at: DOI:10.1007/978-3-031-17475-9_6

HOW IS DAMAGE QUANTIFIED?

A thermoelastic theory was defined in [3] for anisotropic materials and a damage parameter was defined using TSA

- It was developed based in the law of conservation of mass, momentum and energy.
- It relates the density, the internal energy per unit mass and the heat absorbed per unit mass for damaged and undamaged materials.
- Experiments were carried out on **GFRP [0,90,0,90,0]_s** at a loading frequency of **10.1 Hz**

$$\Delta T = -\frac{T_0}{\rho C_p} \cdot (\alpha_x \sigma_x + \alpha_y \sigma_y) \xrightarrow[\text{i.e. the laminate stress}]{\text{In pure tension: } (\alpha_x \sigma_x + \alpha_y \sigma_y)} \frac{\Delta T}{T_0} = K_{Undamaged} \cdot \frac{\Delta \sigma_x}{(1 - D)^2}$$

$-(\alpha_x) / \rho C_p$

* Undamaged: $D=0$
* Damaged: $D \neq 0$

Damage parameter

$$D_{TSA} = 1 - \sqrt{K_{Undamaged} \cdot \Delta \sigma \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta T}{T_0}\right)^{-1}}$$

$$D_{YM} = \frac{E_{Undamaged} - E_{Damaged}}{E_{Undamaged}}$$

NOVELTY OF THIS RESEARCH

- Damage parametrisation carried out at low frequencies → **Subsurface**
- Full-field damage parametrisation → **Localised ROIs**
- Does the D_{TSA} gives better a better quantification of actual damage?

[3] Zhang D, Sandor B (1990) A thermoelasticity theory for damage in anisotropic materials. Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct 13:497–509

EXPERIMENTAL PLAN – MATERIAL (CFRP IM7/8552)

Tension mode → uniform strain state through the laminate thickness

Configuration	Loading scenario	FPF _{Tsai-Wu} (MPa)	Ply failing	Failure Mode	Applied cyclic Stress (MPa)	UTS _{LaRC03} (MPa)
[90,0] _{3S} & [0,90] _{3S}	Tension Loading	542.60	90°	Matrix failure	162.66 ± 141.33	1245.63
[0,45,-45,0,0,0] _S & [0,0,0,45,-45,0] _S	Tension Loading	914.87	±45°	Shear	123.46 ± 111.11	1548.42

- Different plies breaking and different failure mechanisms
- Low cyclic stress must be applied

Coupon Preparation

EXPERIMENTAL PLAN

WE ARE USING TSA AND DIC

**...Why DIC?
To obtain D_{YM}**

Load Ramp **Induce damage progressively (in tension)**

Cyclic Loading **Observe the plies condition (Inspection)**

EXPERIMENTAL ARRANGEMENTS

SAMPLE

DIC
CAMERAS

TSA
CAMERA

LIGHTS

HYDRAULICS

Damage Quantification: Multidirectional laminates

Damage Quantification: Multidirectional laminates

TSA Damage Quantification: All the laminates

CONCLUSIONS OF THE RESEARCH

- Full-Field damage parametrization using TSA **at low frequencies provides** information about both surface and subsurface
- Compared with the stiffness degradation parametrisation, D_{TSA} provides more information about the laminate's status
 1. $[90,0]_{3S}$ wasn't more damaged than $[0,90]_{3S}$ but it exhibited a higher D_{TSA}
 2. $[0,45,-45,0,0,0]_S$ wasn't more damaged than $[0,0,0,45,-45,0]_S$ but it exhibited a higher D_{TSA}

TSA provides a better measure of a **reduction in structural performance** when the damage is close to the surface

FUTURE WORK

- WIP: Damage parametrization of a real structure: **C-Spar**
- Subject specimens to different stress states (e.g. bending) → Not only tension in real structures stress state

WIP: C-Spar // EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

C-Spar in the test machine

Speckled C-Spar

Rafa calibrating the tests

WIP: C-Spar // Inside the web Inspection

Undamaged

Loading Frequency = 3.1 Hz

Wrinkles
High stress concentration areas

8 Shape: Buckling ~ Bending

Damaged

Loading Frequency = 3.1 Hz

Same pattern found as the undamaged

Damage parametrisation

**More complex stress state*

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